

Insect Antifeedant Novel Limonoids from the Roots of *Melia azedarach*

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An extract of the roots of *Melia azedarach* has yielded four new limonoids, azecins 1, 2, 3 and 4, whose structures have been determined by ir, ¹H, ¹³C nmr, uv and mass spectra. The isolated azecins 1 and 3 are effective antifeedants when incorporated into the fourth instar larva of *Spodoptera litura* and third instar of grub stages of brinjal beetle *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* Fabricus. Reduced growth rate and increased time of pupation are evident at lower dose levels while significant mortality is noted at higher dose levels.

Melia azedarach (Meliaceae) is a medicinal plant employed in the indigenous system of medicine¹ and to control insect pests². Earlier studies on this plant had disclosed the presence of fatty acids³, triterpenoids⁴ and santonin². Antifeedant activity directed fractionation of the roots extract of *M. azedarach* utilising larvae of *Spodoptera litura* and *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* Fabricus, has resulted in the isolation of four new limonoids, azecins 1, 2, 3 and 4. Two of these possess unique structural features having allylic alcohol type grouping in ring-A. Compounds of such structures occur rarely in nature.

Results and Discussion

The azecins (1-4) showed some similarities as evidenced by comparison of their spectral data (Tables 1 and 2). Obvious similarities include methyls, acetate methyl singlets, three olefinic protons characteristic of a furan moiety and sugar protons except in 2 which exhibited the presence of -CO-C(Me)=CH(Me) and absence of sugar moiety. Although ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of 1-4 were consistent with the structures shown, additional information was required for complete elucidation of their structures.

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE AZECINS 1-4*

Proton	1	2	3	4
H-1	3.30 dd (2.5 and 4)	4.80 t (3)	6.10 d (10)	6.15 d (10)
H-2	1.80 m	—	6.85 dd (6 and 10)	6.90 dd (6 and 10)
H-3	4.90 dd (4 and 12.5)	3.40 m	3.90 d (6)	3.90 d (6)
H-5	2.60 bd (10.5)	2.90 d (13)	—	—
H-6	2.30 dd (10.5 and 15)	4.10 dd (12.5 and 2.5)	—	—
H-7	—	5.80 d (3)	—	4.60 t (4)
H-9	2.15 dd (1.5 and 5)	—	—	—
H-11	2.30 m	—	—	—
H-12	5.50 dd (5.5 and 11.5)	—	—	—
H-15	4.60 bd (2.5)	5.50 bd (6)	3.60 d (1.5)	3.70 s
H-17	5.70 s	3.40 bd (6)	—	5.60 s
H-30	5.30 s	3.50 ABq (8)	—	—
Me-33	3.45 s	—	—	—
C-Me	0.85, 0.88, 0.90, 1.20 s	1.10, 1.25, 1.50, 1.90 s	0.95, 1.05, 1.08, 1.10, 1.12 s	0.90, 1.05, 1.10, 1.12, 1.16 s
OAc	1.42 and 1.95 s	2.10 s	2.00 s	2.10 s
Furan-H	6.35, 7.30, 7.40 m	6.30, 7.25, 7.30 m	6.40, 7.20, 7.40 m	6.40, 7.20, 7.38 m
Tiglate-	—	—	—	—
H-3'	—	7.00 q (7)	—	—
Me	—	1.85 bd (7)	—	—
Me	—	1.90 bs	—	—
gluc H-1	5.10 d (7)	—	4.40 d (7.5), H-1'	—
			4.60 d (7.6), H-1''	
rham H-1	4.40 d (2)	—	4.38 d (2)	—
arab H-1	—	—	—	4.40 d(6.5)
rham Me	1.15 d (6)	—	1.12 d (6)	—
Sugar-H	5.60-5.80 m	—	5.30-5.50 m	4.90-5.10, 3.60-3.92 m

*The numbers in parentheses represent the coupling constants.

The azecins **1**, **3** and **4** on acid hydrolysis yielded their genins **5**, **6** and **7**, and sugars rutinose (from **1**), rhamnosyl-glucosyl-glucoside (from **3**) and arabinose (from **4**) respectively. The structures of **5-7** were confirmed by the study of their ir, mass, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra and these data were also compared with closely related limonoids isolated by other workers^{1,2,5-8}. The linkages of sugars were confirmed by their anomeric proton signals with coupling constant values. The sequence of the sugars in the azecins **1**, **3** and **4** was also confirmed by partial and specific enzymatic hydrolysis of the azecins **1**, **3** and **4** respectively. The azecin **2** displayed the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data similar to those of ohchinolide A⁶, except at position-3 signals which displayed an exchangeable proton (3-OH).

TABLE 2-¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE AZECINS 1-4

Carbon	1	2	3	4
C-1	78 00	71 80	157 50	159 00
C-2	28 50	27 5	125 30	126 30
C-3	74 00	72 00	78 50	74 00
C-4	38 50	42 5	38 20	38 30
C-5	42 10	40 5	170 00	46 10
C-6	33 20	71 2	138 00	23 80
C-7	173 50	75 1	203 80	71 90
C-8	140 50	45 4	44 70	43 90
C-9	49 50	37 00	43 60	43 20

C-10	43 00	40 2	42 20	42 10
C-11	30 00	32 5	25 80	25 70
C-12	69 00	171 20	78 00	77 90
C-13	47 00	138 50	51 50	47 00
C-14	80 20	148 00	80 20	80 20
C-15	68 50	85 8	68 60	68 60
C-16	174 10	37 5	37 50	174 00
C-17	79 00	47 00	50 50	15 30
C-18	10 00	15 5	22 20	21 90
C-19	22 00	110 00	15 60	15 30
C-20	121 00	126 5	124 50	120 50
C-21	142 00	139 1	140 30	142 10
C-22	110 20	110 00	111 60	110 00
C-23	143 00	143 5	141 40	142 60
C-28	26 50	-	28 00	-
C-29	15 50	-	15 40	-
C-30	114 50	78 10	27 10	-
C-31	169 00	19 50	-	-
C-32	21 00	20 30	-	-
C-33	51 50	-	-	-
C-34	150 00	-	-	-
C-35	20 00	-	-	-
Gluc C-1	101 50	-	(M) 94 90	-
C-2	75 00	-	75 00	-
C-3	78 00	-	76 30	-
C-4	70 00	-	69 40	-
C-5	77 00	-	76 60	-
C-6	63 00	-	68 00	-
Rham C-1	100 50	-	100 00	-
C-2	72 50	-	72 50	-
C-3	70 90	-	70 30	-
C-4	75 20	-	75 70	-
C-5	68 00	-	67 80	-
C-6	17 50	-	17 50	-
OCOCH ₃		21 00	21 20	21 30
OCOCH ₃		169 50	170 40	173 80
Tig C-1'	-	164 50	-	-
C-2'	-	130 20	-	-
C-3'	-	128 60	-	-
C-4'	-	129 00	-	-
C-5'	-	133 60	-	-
Gluc C-1	-	-	103 00	-
C-2	-	-	74 50	-
C-3	-	-	76 40	-
C-4	-	-	70 00	-
C-5	-	-	76 50	-
C-6	-	-	61 00	-
Arab C-1	-	-	-	104 10
C-2	-	-	-	81 00
C-3	-	-	-	72 40
C-4	-	-	-	66 90
C-5	-	-	-	65 10

M represents the middle portion of glucose in **3**

The azecins **1** and **3** showed antifeedant activity against the fourth instar larva of *Spodoptera litura* and third instar of grub stages of brinjal beetle *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* Fabricus by the reported method^{2,9}. Toxicity results for both the insects indicated that continued feeding on diets containing either for **1** and **3** at 200 ppm level would result in about 100% mortality prior to pupation.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (EtOH) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on an Acculab-10 spectrophotometer, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra (CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard) at 500 MHz and 90 MHz on CFT-20 NMR (for ^1H) and 90.56 MHz on Bruker WM 400 (for ^{13}C) spectrometers and mass spectra on a JMS-D-300 spectrometer equipped with a direct inlet system operating at 70 eV. The analytical data for all the azecins and their genin part were within the range of ± 0.06 of the theoretical values.

Extraction and isolation of limonoids : The powdered roots (2 kg) of *M. azedarach* were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet extractor for 32 h. The remaining roots were air-dried and then extracted for additional 32 h with ligroin. The petroleum ether extract yielded 2.3 g, and the ligroin extract yielded 2.0 g of soluble materials.

Fractionation of extracts : Both the petroleum ether and ligroin extracts were initially subjected to CC on a glass column (72 × 6 cm) packed with Si-gel. The petroleum ether fraction was eluted with petroleum ether- C_6H_6 (7 : 3, v/v) and petroleum ether- C_6H_6 (2 : 6, v/v) to yield the azecins **1** and **2**, while the ligroin fraction was eluted with ligroin- C_6H_6 (5 : 5, v/v) and ligroin- C_6H_6 (1 : 9, v/v) to afford the azecins **3** and **4**. All four azecins were obtained as colourless crystalline solids. Tlc monitoring of the fractionation process was carried out on Si-gel (60–254) plates (E. Merck).

Azecin **1** (900 mg), showed m.p. 180–82°; ^1H and ^{13}C nmr (Tables 1 and 2); λ_{max} 217 nm (ϵ 11 800); ν_{max} 2 940, 1 510, 875 (furan), 1 740 (lactone), 1 720 (methyl ester) and 825 cm^{-1} (glycoside). Compound **1** (400 mg) was hydrolysed with H_2SO_4 (7%) to give **5**, L-rhamnose and D-glucose : **5**, m.p. 214–16°, [M^+] 589. Partial acid hydrolysis of **1** yielded L-rhamnose first followed by D-glucose confirming the presence of L-rhamnose as the end-sugar. Azecin **1** on treatment with takadiastase enzyme afforded L-rhamnose and a prolimonoid which on further treatment with almond enzyme gave **5** and D-glucose supporting the presence of rhamnose and glucose in **1**. Methylation ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-K}_2\text{CO}_3$) of **1** followed by acid hydrolysis afforded **5** and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl derivatives of glucose and rhamnose showing the rutinose moiety.

Azecin **2** (700 mg), showed m.p. 215–18°; ^1H and ^{13}C nmr (Tables 1 and 2); λ_{max} 230, 270 and 282 nm (ϵ 16 000 1 200 and 900); ν_{max} 3 300 (OH), 3 080, 2 950, 1 725, 1 640, 1 500 and 870 cm^{-1} , [M^+] 582.

Azecin **3** (800 mg), gave m.p. 222–25°; ^1H and ^{13}C nmr (Tables 1 and 2); λ_{max} 239 and 210 nm (ϵ 8 000 and

10 000); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH), 2 950, 1 505 and 875 (furan), 1 690 (CO), 1 770 and 1 725 cm^{-1} (enolic acetate). Compound **3** (500 mg) was hydrolysed with H_2SO_4 (7%) to afford **6**, D-glucose and L-rhamnose : **6**, m.p. 280–82°d, [M^+] 486. Permethylation of azecin **3**, according to the method of Hakomori, followed by treatment with 5% HCl-MeOH afforded **6**, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose; 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose confirming triose moiety having 2 moles of glucose and 1 mole of rhamnose. Partial acid hydrolysis of **3** yielded L-rhamnose and 6-acetoxy-7-oxo-14 β ,15 β -epoxymeliac-1,5-diene-3-*O*-gentiobioside [^{13}C nmr of sugar: gluc(t) : 102.8 (C1), 73.3 (C2), 76.5 (C3), 70.3 (C4), 76.5 (C5), 61.0 (C6); gluc: 94.1 (C1), 72.2 (C2), 76.6 (C3), 69.5 (C4), 76.2 (C5), 68.1 (C6)].

Azecin **4** (800 mg), showed m.p. 160–63°d; ^1H and ^{13}C nmr (Tables 1 and 2); λ_{max} 285 and 210 nm (ϵ 10 000 and 9 400); ν_{max} 3 450 (OH), 2 940, 1 500 and 870 (furan), 1 740 (lactone), 1 720 (acetate) and 820 cm^{-1} (glycoside). Compound **4** (400 mg) was hydrolysed with H_2SO_4 (7%) to give **7** and L-arabinose.

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